

United States Department of the Interior

FISH AND WILDLIFE SERVICE
San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office
U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service
650 Capitol Mall, Suite 8-300
Sacramento, CA 95814

In Reply Refer To:
08FBDT00-2020-F-0111

October 5, 2020

Kavita Mak
Environmental Engineer, WIFIA Program
U.S. Environmental Protection Agency
William Jefferson Clinton Building
1200 Pennsylvania Avenue, N. W.
Mail Code: 4202M
Washington, DC 20460

Subject: Formal Section 7 Consultation on the City of Sunnyvale's Cleanwater Program
Phase 2 Project

Dear Ms. Mak:

This letter is in response to the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency's (EPA) February 19, 2020 request for initiation of informal consultation with the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (Service) on the proposed City of Sunnyvale's Cleanwater Program Phase 2 Project (proposed project) in the City of Sunnyvale, Santa Clara County, California. Your request was received by the Service on February 24, 2020. The EPA determined the proposed project may affect, but is not likely to adversely affect the federally endangered California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*), California least tern (*Sterna antillarum browni*), and salt marsh harvest mouse (*Reithrodontomys raviventris*). Regarding taxonomic assignment and nomenclature for the California clapper rail, until a time when the Service officially adopts changes made by the American Ornithologists' Union (from California clapper rail [*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*] to Ridgway's Rail [*Rallus obsoletus obsoletus*]), the Service maintains the use of California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*) as used in this current correspondence. This response is provided under the authority of the Endangered Species Act of 1973, as amended (16 U.S.C. 1531 *et seq.*) (Act), and in accordance with the implementing regulations pertaining to interagency cooperation (50 CFR 402).

In reviewing this project, the Service has relied upon: (1) the EPA's February 19, 2020 letter requesting consultation with the enclosed Biological Resources Technical Report dated September 2018; (2) the 2nd revised Biological Resources Technical Report dated August 2020; (3) a conference call and numerous emails between the EPA, Service, City of Sunnyvale, and consultants; and (4) other information available to the Service.

The Service concurs that the proposed project is not likely to adversely affect the California least tern. The Action Area does not contain suitable nesting habitat and the wastewater treatment ponds and adjacent channels are not considered suitable habitat for terns that may be foraging in South San Francisco Bay.

The Service does not concur with the EPA's determination that the proposed project is not likely to adversely affect the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail due to potential effects to individuals from noise disturbance and the implementation of certain *Conservation Measures*. Therefore, the remainder of this document is the Service's biological opinion on the effects of the proposed project on the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse.

Consultation History

February 24, 2020	The Service received a request from the EPA for informal consultation on the City of Sunnyvale's Cleanwater Program Phase 2 Project.
March 13, 2020	The Service sent an email requesting additional information from the EPA regarding the project description and species effects.
May 27, 2020	The Service received additional information in an email from the EPA.
May 28, 2020	The Service sent an email to the EPA asking clarifying questions.
June 8, 2020	The Service participated in a conference call with the EPA, City of Sunnyvale, and consultants.
August 13, 2020	The Service received the 1 st revised Biological Resources Technical Report dated August 2020 and in-email answers to the Service's May 28, 2020 questions.
August 14, 2020	The Service sent an email to the EPA asking clarifying questions.
September 1, 2020	The Service received the 2 nd revised Biological Resources Technical Report dated August 2020 from the EPA.
September 9-10, 2020	The Service and EPA exchanged emails. The EPA confirmed their not likely to adversely affect determinations.

BIOLOGICAL OPINION

Description of the Proposed Action

The Cleanwater Program Phase 2 Project is a rehabilitation project of the Sunnyvale Water Pollution Control Plant (WPCP). The major components of the proposed project are summarized below. Please refer to the 2nd revised August 2020 Biological Resources Technical Report for a more detailed project description. Operation of the WPCP will change following construction of the proposed project but is not expected to affect listed species and will not be addressed in this document.

Treatment Facility Rehabilitation

Major elements of rehabilitation of the WPCP's existing secondary and tertiary treatment facilities include:

- Reline and/or replace influent pipelines up to 48-inch diameter that convey raw sewage to the WPCP;
- Reline the 66-inch-diameter primary effluent pipeline that conveys primary wastewater to the oxidation ponds;
- Rehab two of three 92-foot-diameter fixed growth reactors that nitrify wastewater after the oxidation ponds;
- Rehab two of four 60-foot-diameter air flotation tanks that remove algae and other suspended solids produced during secondary treatment;
- Replace equipment in the four 960-square foot dual media filters that remove suspended solids from the final effluent;
- Repair concrete, replace mechanical equipment, and seismically strengthen the four chlorine contact tanks that disinfect the wastewater prior to discharge or reuse.

New Secondary and Bio-solids Treatment Facilities

This component includes construction of a new secondary and solids handling facilities project, including new conventional activated sludge treatment facilities, a maintenance building, a thickening and dewatering facility, a floodwall, a standby generator and fuel tank, and electrical and piping improvements.

New Support Facilities

The component includes the reconstruction of support facilities necessary to operate the plant, including a new Administration and Laboratory Building.

Facility Demolition

The existing primary sedimentation basins, maintenance shop, administration building, and primary control building would be demolished.

Timing

Project construction will occur within normal City working hours, weekdays between the hours of 7:00 a.m. and 6:00 p.m., and, as approved on an “exception basis”, Saturdays between 8:00 a.m. and 5:00 p.m. Temporary, manual lighting would be installed in locations where night work is performed, and would be removed after construction activities are complete. The Biological Resources Technical Report did not define when or where night work will occur. The proposed project construction is expected to start in May 2021 and end in August 2025.

Equipment

Heavy equipment used for construction activities includes: an excavator; grader, haul trucks, dozer/loader; roller; forklift; drill rigs; paving equipment; concrete trucks; water trucks; crawler and rough terrain cranes; pile drivers; and pickup trucks.

Construction Activities

Most of the construction activities will generally require excavation, demolition, and hauling of materials. The maximum depth of excavation during construction would be approximately 32 feet deep. Approximately 300,000 cubic yards of material would be excavated over the course of project construction.

Construction of the projects will generally take place within the main plant, with the exception of work done at the Recycle Yard and oxidation pond facilities. Proposed improvements at multiple facilities will not involve ground-disturbing activities, but will instead include equipment installation and replacement of existing above-ground structures.

Pile drivers will be the loudest equipment used during construction. For the site preparation and existing plant rehabilitation, piles will be driven or augered to approximately 40 feet below ground surface to support temporary shoring during excavation activities associated with buried piping within the main plant. Auger cast piles will be used for structural foundation improvements associated with construction of secondary treatment and dewatering facilities, also within the main plant. The northern alignment of the perimeter wall will be constructed as a slurry wall, which involves excavation of a trench that is filled with a mud-water slurry before concrete is piped into the trench starting at the bottom of the trench, and would not require pile driving.

Local dewatering will be necessary for perimeter wall construction, yard piping replacement, demolition of the auxiliary pump station, sanitary sewer vault construction, demolition of primary sedimentation tanks, demolition of the primary control building, cleanwater center excavation and secondary treatment and dewatering facilities excavation. Dewatered groundwater will be routed towards the WPCP storm drain system, which is then routed to the preliminary treatment facilities.

The primary effluent and pond effluent pipelines will be rehabilitated with cured in place methods that would not require ground disturbance. Pipelines within the main plant and Carl Road, including the new secondary effluent pipeline and influent sewer pipelines, will be constructed via methods that involve trenching.

As part of the existing plant rehabilitation and site preparation, the City of Sunnyvale will remove vegetation and add fill to match surrounding grade along the northern wall boundary and near the Carl Road and Borregas Avenue intersection. Non-hazardous waste will be disposed of at any landfill within Santa Clara County, while hazardous waste if present will be sent to an appropriate disposal site.

Conservation Measures

The City of Sunnyvale modified a select number of their *Sunnyvale Water Pollution Control Plant Master Plan Program Environmental Impact Report* mitigation measures to apply specifically to the proposed project. The Service modified them further in this document to remove species that are not federally listed and to replace Ridgway's rail with California clapper rail.

1. *Mitigation Measure BIO-2a: Worker Environmental Awareness Training.*

The City of Sunnyvale will retain, or require the contractor to retain, a qualified biologist to conduct mandatory contractor/worker environmental awareness training for all construction personnel working on project activities outside of the main plant. The awareness training will be provided to all construction personnel to brief them on the potential for special-status species to occur on the site, the need to avoid effects to special-status species and their habitats, and all project mitigation measures pertaining to biological resources and water quality. If new construction personnel are added, the contractor will ensure that the personnel receive the mandatory training before starting work. A representative will be appointed during the employee education program to be the contact for any employee or contractor who might inadvertently kill or injure a special-status species or who finds a dead, injured, or entrapped individual. The representative's name and telephone number will be provided to the City of Sunnyvale prior to the initiation of construction activities outside of the main plant.

2. *Mitigation Measure BIO-2b: Minimization of Impacts on Water Quality.*

The following will be incorporated into the construction stormwater pollution prevention plan and implemented during construction to avoid or minimize impacts on water quality:

- Earth-moving in areas draining to wetlands and aquatic habitats will not occur during days when rain is occurring or predicted to occur (i.e., greater than 40 percent chance) during the work period. This measure applies to all project areas with potential to drain to wetlands or aquatic habitats, particularly in or adjacent to Sunnyvale West Channel, Cargill Channel, Moffett Channel, Ponds 1 and 2, and Santa Clara Valley Water District Pond A4.

- All permit conditions, legal requirements, and appropriate dredging and engineering practices shall be followed to avoid and minimize water quality impacts. Suitable erosion control, sediment control, source control, treatment control, material management, and stormwater management Best Management Practices will be implemented consistent with the latest edition of the California Stormwater Quality Association “Stormwater Best Management Practices Handbook,” available at www.casqa.org.
- Spill prevention kits shall always be in close proximity when using hazardous materials (e.g., crew trucks and other logical locations). Feasible measures shall be implemented to ensure that hazardous materials are properly handled and the quality of aquatic resources is protected by all reasonable means when removing vegetation and sediments from the channels.
- No fueling shall be done in areas immediately adjacent to (i.e., within 50 feet of) channels, ponds, or wetlands. For stationary equipment that must be fueled on site, containment shall be provided in such a manner that any accidental spill of fuel shall not be able to enter the water or contaminate sediments that may come in contact with water. Any equipment that is readily moved out of the channels, ponds, or wetlands shall not be fueled in these sensitive habitat areas or the immediate floodplains surrounding them.
- A hazardous materials management/fuel spill containment plan will be developed and implemented by the construction contractor and given to all contractors and biological monitors, with at least one copy of the plan located onsite at all times. The purpose of the plan is to provide onsite construction managers, environmental compliance monitors, and regulatory agencies with a detailed description of hazardous materials management, spill prevention, and spill response/cleanup measures associated with the construction activities. The primary objective of the plan is to prevent a spill of hazardous materials. Elements of the plan will include, but are not limited to the following:
 - A discussion of hazardous materials management, including delineation of hazardous material and hazardous waste storage area, access and egress routes, waterways, emergency assembly areas, and temporary hazardous waste storage areas;
 - Materials Safety Data Sheets for all chemicals used and stored on site;
 - An inventory list of emergency equipment;
 - Spill control and countermeasures including employee spill prevention/response training;
 - Notification and documentation procedures; and

- Monthly reporting plan.
- Vehicles will be checked daily for oil or fuel leaks and will be washed only at an approved area (existing construction yards or legally operating car washes). No washing of vehicles will occur in work areas located outside of the main plant fence line.
- The work site, areas adjacent to the site, and access areas will be maintained in an orderly condition, free and clear from debris and discarded materials. This measure includes work areas located outside of the main plant fence line. Personnel will not sweep, grade, or flush surplus materials, rubbish, debris, or dust onto adjacent areas or waterways. Upon completion of work, all building materials, debris, unused materials, concrete forms, and other construction-related materials will be removed from work areas located outside of the main plant fence line.
- Stockpiled materials outside of the main plant fence line will be covered by plastic sheeting, tarps, or similar material that can be secured during wind and rain. A sediment fence or berm will be installed around stockpiled dredged material to prevent runoff from transporting sediment into sensitive habitats (such as the channels, ponds, and wetlands). Heavy equipment will not be operated in the active channels or within wetland habitats, but instead from existing hardscape, access roads, and levees.
- Water conservation methods will ensure that water used in the work area does not create surface flows capable of carrying pollutants to the nearby creek channel. All personnel, including sub-contractors will be instructed on the practical methods of preventing leaks or over-use of watering, and will be required to adhere to the practices in the detail sheets provided. Woody debris from tree trimming, and other activities will not be left in the active channels or in wetland habitats.
- Silt fencing will be used to the extent feasible during construction and maintenance activities that could potentially result in substantial siltation of open water.

3. *Mitigation Measure BIO-2f: California Clapper Rail Measures.*

The following will be implemented for activities outside of the main plant fence line to avoid and minimize impacts on California clapper rails, particularly in tidal marsh habitats associated with the Moffett Channel:

- Impacts on tidal wetland habitat of these species will be avoided. Tidal wetland habitat for these species occurs in the northern portions of the work area, in association with Moffett Channel. Suitable tidal wetland habitat for this species is not present within the main plant fence line.

- To avoid causing the abandonment of an active nest, construction activities within 700 feet of vegetated tidal marsh providing suitable breeding habitat for California clapper rails (i.e., the area along Moffett Channel north of the point where the marsh widens near the pond circulation pump station) will be avoided during the breeding season from February 1 through August 31.
- Aside from continued use of recreational trails established prior to the start of the breeding season (which may continue), only routine inspection, maintenance, or monitoring activities that have little potential for effects on rails due to their short durations, distance from rail habitat, or low-magnitude effects may be performed during the breeding season in areas within or adjacent to rail breeding habitat. Otherwise, with the Service and California Department of Fish and Wildlife approval on a case-by-case basis, construction activities may take place after July 15 in a given area if the activity is thought to be minimally disturbing to breeding rails.
- The extent of impacts near tidal marsh will be clearly demarcated in the field prior to construction, and no impacts (including construction access) will occur outside those limits.
- Silt fencing or similar material will be installed at the perimeter of work areas, between all areas of earth-moving and marsh to prevent dirt and other materials from entering marsh areas that are not intended to be affected.
- No animals can be brought to the project site to avoid harassing, killing, or injuring wildlife.
- The project site will be maintained trash-free, and food refuse will be contained in secure bins and removed daily during construction and dredging.
- Nighttime work near tidal marsh habitat will be avoided.

4. *Mitigation Measure BIO-2g: Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse Measures.*

The following measures will be implemented for activities outside of the main plant fence line to avoid and minimize impacts on the salt marsh harvest mouse particularly by marsh habitat associated with Moffett Channel and Cargill Channel:

- Impacts on pickleweed and wetland habitat that may support this species will be avoided. Wetland habitat that may support these species occurs in the northern portion of the work area, in association with Moffett Channel and Cargill Channel. No suitable habitat for these species occurs within the main plant fence line.
- To avoid the loss of individual harvest mice, no excavation, fill, or construction activities in suitable habitat, vegetation removal and fill in marsh habitats,

including the Moffett Channel and the Cargill Channel, will occur.

- Exclusion fencing will be erected as needed between construction areas and harvest mouse habitat to define and isolate protected habitat for this species. This fencing will consist of heavy plastic sheeting or metal material that cannot be climbed by harvest mice, or similar Service-approved exclusion materials, buried at least 4 inches below the ground's surface and with at least 1 foot (but no more than 4 feet) above the ground. All supports for the fencing will be placed on the inside of the work area. A 4-foot buffer will be maintained free of vegetation around the outside of the exclusion fencing. The fencing will be inspected daily during construction, and any necessary repairs will be made within 24 hours of when damage is found. If any breaks in the fencing are found, a qualified biologist will inspect the work area for salt marsh harvest mice. If any individual harvest mice are found within the impact footprint, they will be allowed to move on their own to vegetated areas outside the impact footprint.
- During construction in areas where salt marsh harvest mice may be affected, a qualified biologist will check underneath vehicles and equipment for this species before such equipment is moved during each day of construction, unless the equipment is surrounded by exclusion fencing.

Action Area

The Action Area is defined in 50 CFR § 402.02, as “all areas to be affected directly or indirectly by the Federal action and not merely the immediate area involved in the action.” The Action Area for this consultation encompasses all areas that may be directly or indirectly affected as a result of activities for the project and the broader area that, while outside the project footprint, may be directly or indirectly affected by vibrations, noise, lighting, or movement associated with the proposed project. Specifically, the Action Area includes: the main plant area and the oxidation ponds; portions of Cargill Channel, Moffett Channel, Sunnyvale West Channel, Ponds 1 and 2, and Santa Clara Valley Water District Pond A4; and adjacent marsh areas. The Biological Resources Technical Report did not quantify the acreage of the Action Area; therefore, the Service estimates the total Action Area to be approximately 60 acres.

Analytical Framework for the Jeopardy Determination

Section 7(a)(2) of the Act requires that Federal agencies ensure that any action they authorize, fund, or carry out is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of listed species. “Jeopardize the continued existence of” means to engage in an action that reasonably will be expected, directly or indirectly, to reduce appreciably the likelihood of both the survival and recovery of a listed species in the wild by reducing the reproduction, numbers, or distribution of that species (50 CFR § 402.02).

The jeopardy analysis in this biological opinion considers the effects of the proposed Federal action, and any cumulative effects, on the rangewide survival and recovery of the listed species. It relies on four components: (1) the *Status of the Species*, which describes the current

rangewide condition of the species, the factors responsible for that condition, and its survival and recovery needs; (2) the *Environmental Baseline*, which analyzes the current condition of the species in the Action Area without the consequences to the listed species caused by the proposed action, the factors responsible for that condition, and the relationship of the Action Area to the survival and recovery of the species; (3) the *Effects of the Action*, which includes all effects that are caused by the proposed Federal action; and (4) the *Cumulative Effects*, which evaluates the effects of future, non-Federal activities in the Action Area on the species. The *Effects of the Action* and *Cumulative Effects* are added to the *Environmental Baseline* and in light of the *Status of the Species*, the Service formulates its opinion as to whether the proposed action is likely to jeopardize the continued existence of listed species.

Status of the Species

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

There are two subspecies of the salt marsh harvest mouse: the northern subspecies (*R. r. halicoetes*) and the southern subspecies (*R. r. raviventris*) both of which are listed as endangered. For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the species' range-wide status, please refer to the *Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California*, available at: https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/recovery_plan/TMRP/20130923_TMRP_Books_Signed_FINAL.pdf (Service 2013). Critical habitat has not been designated for this species. Threats evaluated during the drafting of the recovery plan and discussed in the final document have continued to act on the species since its publication, with loss of habitat being the most significant effect. The Service is in the process of developing our current 5-year review for the species.

California Clapper Rail

Information about the California clapper rail biology and ecology is available in the *Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California*, available at: https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/recovery_plan/TMRP/20130923_TMRP_Books_Signed_FINAL.pdf (Service 2013). Critical habitat has not been designated for this species. For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the species' range-wide status, please refer to the California clapper rail 5-year Review, available at https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/five_year_review/doc6592.pdf (Service 2020). No change in the species' listing status was recommended in this 5-year review. Threats evaluated during that review and discussed in the final document have continued to act on the species with loss of habitat being the most significant effect.

Environmental Baseline

Environmental Baseline refers to the condition of the listed species or its designated critical habitat in the Action Area, without the consequences to the listed species or designated critical habitat caused by the proposed action. The *Environmental Baseline* includes the past and present impacts of all Federal, State, or private actions and other human activities in the Action Area, the anticipated impacts of all proposed Federal projects in the Action Area that have already undergone formal or early section 7 consultation, and the impact of State or private actions which are contemporaneous with the consultation in process. The consequences to listed species

or designated critical habitat from ongoing agency activities or existing agency facilities that are not within the agency's discretion to modify are part of the *Environmental Baseline*.

Developed and Landscaped Areas

Within the Action Area, developed areas consist of the main plant facilities, graveled maintenance roads located within the existing graded area for the project, and hardscape, such as parking lots and streets of Borregas Avenue and Carl Road.

Within the WPCP, landscaped habitat consists of small maintained areas in the main plant facilities that support oleander (*Nerium oleander*) shrubs and mature trees, including various species of eucalyptus (primarily *Eucalyptus globulus* and *E. camaldulensis*), pepper tree (*Schinus molle*), coast redwood (*Sequoia sempervirens*), alder (*Alnus* sp.), and pine (*Pinus* sp.). Ice plant (*Carpobrotus* sp.) occurs in the understory of landscaped habitat in some areas.

Ruderal Non-native Grassland

Ruderal/non-native grassland occurs in small patches in the WPCP, north of the WPCP, and throughout areas east and west of Borregas Avenue in the Action Area. This habitat type is dominated by non-native grasses and forbs, including various species of wild oats (*Avena* spp.), smilo grass (*Stipa miliacea*), common fennel (*Foeniculum vulgare*), Italian thistle (*Carduus pycnocephalus*), bull mallow (*Malva nicaeensis*), stinkwort (*Dittrichia graveolens*), and the highly invasive broadleaved pepperweed (*Lepidium latifolium*). Wildlife use of ruderal grasslands in much of the Action Area is limited by human disturbance, the limited extent of grassland areas, and the isolation of habitat remnants from more extensive grasslands.

Northern Coastal Salt Marsh

Northern coastal salt marsh is present in the Action Area only as a narrow strip along the Cargill Channel. Although the Cargill Channel is blocked from tidal influence, open water habitat and soils are sufficiently saline to support northern coastal salt marsh. This habitat is dominated by hydrophytic and salt-tolerant native forbs, such as pickleweed (*Sarcocornia pacifica*), Pacific cordgrass (*Spartina foliosa*), and alkali heath (*Frankenia salina*), as well as non-native oppositeleaf Russian thistle (*Salsola soda*).

Coastal Brackish Marsh

Coastal brackish marsh is present within and directly adjacent to the Sunnyvale West Channel and the upper portions of the marsh along the Moffett Channel. Coastal brackish marsh is present where vegetation is subject to tidal inundation but diluted by freshwater flows (from upstream and from WPCP releases), such as along the Sunnyvale West Channel and Moffett Channel.

Coastal brackish marsh is dominated by emergent, vascular plant species adapted to intermediate (brackish) soil and water salinities. Short bulrushes such as sturdy bulrush (*Bolboschoenus robustus*) and alkali bulrush (*Bolboschoenus maritimus*) are key indicator species for this habitat type, and tend to co-dominate coastal brackish marsh with tall bulrushes, such as California

bulrush (*Schoenoplectus californicus*) and hard-stemmed bulrush (*Schoenoplectus acutus*). Other common plant species that occur in this habitat include various species of cattails (*Typha* spp.), smartweed (*Persicaria punctata*), and broadleaved pepperweed (*Lepidium latifolium*).

Coastal brackish marshes in the Action Area are limited in extent and are fairly disturbed. Patches of brackish marsh within the Action Area are located adjacent to maintenance roads where moderate levels of human disturbance (e.g., from vehicles and pedestrians) occur regularly.

Open Water

Cargill Channel is enclosed by levees; it is connected to the non-tidal Santa Clara Valley Water District Pond A4 by a siphon as well as to a managed pond west of Pond 2, which in turn is connected to the San Francisco Bay with a flap gate. Therefore, the Cargill Channel receives some water from Guadalupe Slough when the flap gate is open, but it is not a tidal waterbody. This channel was recently acquired by the Service as part of Don Edwards San Francisco Bay National Wildlife Refuge.

The Sunnyvale West Channel is a linear, channelized drainage feature that has full tidal influence from the similar but much larger Moffett Channel, which connects to Guadalupe Slough and drains to San Francisco Bay. Open water portions of the Sunnyvale West Channel receive freshwater inputs from precipitation, stormwater and irrigation runoff, and effluent from the WPCP.

Ponds 1 and 2 are open water habitat that have been closed off from tidal influence and have been continually used for waste treatment for nearly 50 years.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

As stated in the Biological Resources Technical Report, the coastal salt marsh present in the Action Area within Cargill Channel is very narrow and is disconnected from suitable habitat along the Moffett Channel by an exposed levee road. This marsh does contain a small amount of suitable pickleweed habitat, but the distance from known to be occupied larger marshes like Guadalupe Slough reduces the habitat quality so that it would support at most a very low number of individuals. The brackish tidal marsh in Moffett Channel north of the plant is considered potential salt marsh harvest mouse habitat but the vegetation is fragmented and like the coast marsh described above, the potential for salt marsh harvest mice to occur in these marshes is fairly low but cannot be discounted.

Salt marsh harvest mice are not expected to occur in coastal brackish marsh dominated by pure stands of cattail and California bulrush along Sunnyvale West Channel and Moffett Channel adjacent to the main plant or in the small amounts of brackish marsh in Cargill Channel and Ponds 1 and 2 where patches are isolated and narrow (10 feet wide or less).

California Clapper Rail

California clapper rails have been documented in low densities in Guadalupe Slough, north of the Action Area during the breeding season surveys for the Invasive Spartina Program (Olofson Environmental, Inc. 2020). However as stated in the Biological Resources Technical Report, only marginally suitable nesting habitat is located within the Action Area, in the vicinity of the pond circulation pump station. The quality of the nesting habitat decreases upstream (i.e., south toward the main plant) on Moffett Channel from Guadalupe Slough, as the number of channels and the amount of alkali bulrush and marsh gumplant decreases with distance from the Bay and freshwater vegetation (e.g., tules, common reed) becomes predominant; marsh gumplant is not present in Moffett Channel about 500 feet south of the pond circulation pump station and tules cover over 50 percent of the marsh.

While nesting isn't likely to occur within the Action Area, California clapper rails may forage in the tule- and common reed-dominated brackish marsh in Moffett Channel further south, to the confluence with Sunnyvale West Channel, with decreasing probability as the habitat suitability diminishes with declining salinity, to the point where rails would only use the freshwater marsh at the southern (upstream) extent of Moffett Channel for foraging on rare occasions. The small strip of salt marsh in Cargill Channel is not expected to be used for foraging because it is not connected to tidal marsh. Moffett Channel immediately north of the main plant and Sunnyvale West Channel upstream of Moffett Channel are narrow with steep banks and lack suitable vegetative cover.

Effects of the Action

Effects of the Action are all consequences to listed species or critical habitat that are caused by the proposed action, including the consequences of other activities that are caused by the proposed action. A consequence is caused by the proposed action if it would not occur but for the proposed action and it is reasonably certain to occur. Effects of the Action may occur later in time and may include consequences occurring outside the immediate area involved in the action.

Construction activities will take place within or adjacent to the existing footprints of the facilities and access roads. Marsh habitat will not be physically affected.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

Equipment noise and vibration may interfere with normal behaviors. These behaviors include feeding, sheltering, movement between refugia and foraging grounds, and other essential behaviors. Intolerable levels of disturbance that may force individual mice to flush from cover or prevent them from seeking available cover could expose them to a predation risk that otherwise would not occur (see the noise discussion in the California Clapper Rail section below). Implementation of *Conservation Measure 4-Mitigation Measure BIO-2g: Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse Measures* as it relates to fencing may result in trapping mice in the work area, which could result in injury or mortality. Given the lack of high-quality habitat near the construction areas, the Service anticipates the number of mice to experience these effects will be low.

California Clapper Rail

California clapper rails that may be foraging during construction activities will be subject to visual and noise disturbances. Existing operations provide a baseline level of disturbance, but construction noise will exceed baseline conditions. ESA conducted a modeled noise analysis to determine where construction noise would exceed baseline conditions in potentially suitable habitat. Noise monitoring location LT-1 at Sunnyvale West Channel is immediately west of the main plant and does not provide suitable marsh habitat for California rails, location LT-2 is situated at the confluence of Sunnyvale West Channel and Moffett Channel immediately north of the main plant and represents marginal habitat, and location LT-3 is on the levee west of Moffett Channel between the two pump stations, bordering potential foraging habitat. Existing ambient noise was measured at 57 to 61 A-weighted decibel (dBA) at three noise monitoring locations LT-1 (ESA 2020). According to Barber *et al.* (2009), noise levels above 3 dBA above background levels can result in a 50 percent reduced listening area and 30 percent reduced alerting distance in wildlife while noise levels above 10 dBA above background levels can result in 90 percent reduced alerting distance.

Noise from construction activities at the Pond Circulation Pump Station is estimated to be approximately 69 dBA near LT-3, exceeding the ambient noise by about 10 dbA (ESA 2020). Per the Biological Resources Technical Report, California clapper rails in approximately 1.8 acres of marginally suitable breeding and foraging habitat will be affected by construction activity noise at this location. Adverse effects to breeding individuals near the Pond Circulation Pump Station will be avoided by implementing seasonal work restrictions described in *Conservation Measure 3. Mitigation Measure BIO-2f: California Clapper Rail Measures*.

As stated in the Biological Resources Technical Report, at LT-2, modeled noise from perimeter wall construction exceeds ambient noise levels by 34.6 dBA, and modeled noise from CIPP/mortar lining exceeded ambient noise levels by 7.4 dBA (refer to values under the column titled "Increase Over Ambient at LT (dBA)" for LT-2 in Table 3 of [ESA 2020]). Modeled noise from perimeter wall construction attenuates to measured ambient levels 603 feet from the location of the perimeter wall closest to LT-2, and modeled noise form CIPP/mortar lining attenuates to measured ambient levels 603 feet from the CIPP/mortar lining construction activity. California clapper rails in approximately 2.7 acres of coastal brackish marsh marginally suitable for foraging habitat near LT-2 will be affected by increased noise from construction activities.

Cumulative Effects

Cumulative Effects include the effects of future State, Tribal, local or private actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the Action Area considered in this biological opinion. Future Federal actions unrelated to the proposed project are not considered in this section, because they require separate consultation pursuant to section 7 of the Act. During this consultation, the Service did not identify any future non-Federal actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the Action Area of the proposed project.

Conclusion

After reviewing the current *Status of the Species* for salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail, the *Environmental Baseline* for the Action Area, the *Effects of the Action*, and the

Cumulative Effects, it is the Service's biological opinion that the proposed project is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail. The Service reached this conclusion because the project-related effects to the species, when added to the environmental baseline and analyzed in consideration of all potential cumulative effects, will not rise to the level of appreciably reducing the likelihood of survival or recovery of the species based on the following: (1) based on habitat quality, these species likely only occur in low numbers adjacent to the WPCP; (2) construction effects like noise disturbance are expected to extend only into lower quality habitat; and (3) no physical disturbance to habitat will occur.

INCIDENTAL TAKE STATEMENT

Section 9 of the Act and Federal regulation pursuant to section 4(d) of the Act prohibit the take of endangered and threatened species, respectively, without special exemption. Take is defined as to harass, harm, pursue, hunt, shoot, wound, kill, trap, capture or collect, or to attempt to engage in any such conduct. Harass is defined by Service regulations at 50 CFR § 17.3 as an intentional or negligent act or omission which creates the likelihood of injury to a listed species by annoying it to such an extent as to significantly disrupt normal behavioral patterns which include, but are not limited to, breeding, feeding or sheltering. Harm is defined by the same regulations as an act which actually kills or injures wildlife. Harm is further defined to include significant habitat modification or degradation that results in death or injury to listed species by significantly impairing essential behavioral patterns including breeding, feeding, or sheltering. Incidental take is defined as take that is incidental to, and not the purpose of, the carrying out of an otherwise lawful activity. Under the terms of section 7(b)(4) and section 7(o)(2), taking incidental to and not intended as part of the agency action is not considered to be prohibited taking under the Act, provided that such taking is in compliance with the terms and conditions of this Incidental Take Statement.

The measures described below are non-discretionary, and must be undertaken by the EPA so that they become binding conditions of any grant or permit issued to the applicants, as appropriate, for the exemption in section 7(o)(2) to apply. The EPA has a continuing duty to regulate the activity covered by this incidental take statement. If the EPA (1) fails to assume and implement the terms and conditions, or (2) fails to require the (applicants) to adhere to the terms and conditions of the incidental take statement through enforceable terms that are added to the permit or grant document, the protective coverage of section 7(o)(2) may lapse. In order to monitor the impact of incidental take, the EPA must report the progress of the action and its impact on the species to the Service as specified in the incidental take statement [50 CFR § 402.14(i)(3)]

Amount or Extent of Take

The Service anticipates incidental take of salt marsh harvest mice and California clapper rails will be difficult to detect or quantify for the following reasons: their inherently elusive behavior, their propensity to move rapidly through vegetation, and their cryptic occupancy of vegetation types resulting in low detectability. There is a risk of injury or mortality as a result of the proposed activities. Therefore, the Service anticipates take incidental to the proposed action in the form of injury, or mortality of all salt marsh harvest mice within the approximately 60-acre

Action Area that may become entrapped behind the proposed fencing. The Service anticipates take incidental to the proposed action in the form of harm, by impairing essential behaviors such as foraging or predator evasion, of all salt marsh harvest mice and California clapper rails in the salt and brackish marsh habitat adjacent to the construction areas with the approximately 60-acre Action Area. Upon implementation of the following reasonable and prudent measures, incidental take of salt marsh harvest mice and California clapper rails associated with the project will become exempt from the prohibitions described in section 9 of the Act. No other forms of take are exempted under this opinion.

Effect of the Take

In the accompanying biological opinion, the Service determined that the level of anticipated take is not likely to jeopardize the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail.

Reasonable and Prudent Measure

All necessary and appropriate measures to avoid or minimize effects on the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail resulting from implementation of this project have been incorporated into the project's proposed *Conservation Measures*. Therefore, the Service believes the following reasonable and prudent measure is necessary and appropriate to minimize the incidental take of the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail:

1. The EPA through the applicant and its contractors will minimize the potential incidental take of the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail.

Terms and Condition

In order to be exempt from the prohibitions of section 9 of the Act, the EPA shall ensure compliance with the following term and condition, which implement the reasonable and prudent measure described above. This Term and Condition is non-discretionary.

1. Term and Condition 1 implements Reasonable and Prudent Measure 1:
 - a. At least 15 days prior to the proposed project implementation, the EPA and/or the applicant will submit to the Service, for approval, the name(s) and credentials of biologists it requests to be biological monitors specified for this proposed project. Information included in a request for authorization must include, at a minimum: (1) relevant education; (2) relevant training on species identification, survey techniques, handling individuals of different age classes, and handling of different life stages by a permitted biologist or recognized species expert authorized for such activities by the Service; (3) a summary of field experience conducting requested activities (to include project/research information and actual experience with the species); (4) a summary of biological opinions and/or informal consultations under which they were authorized to work with the listed species and at what level (such as construction monitoring versus handling), this should also include the names and qualifications of persons under which the work was

supervised as well as the amount of work experience on the actual project including detail on whether the species was encountered or not; and (5) a list of 10(a)(1)(A) permits, if any, held or under which individuals are authorized to work with the species (to include permit number, authorized activities, and name of permit holder).

- b. The EPA shall minimize the potential for harm, killing or other forms of take of the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail from project-related activities by implementation of the *Conservation Measures* proposed in the Description of the Proposed Action in this biological opinion.
- c. The EPA shall ensure that their applicant immediately notifies the Service of any killed, injured, or entrapped salt marsh harvest mice or California clapper rail, within one (1) working day of the detection. Please contact the Assistant Field Supervisor of the Endangered Species Division at: San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office, 650 Capitol Mall, Suite 8-300, Sacramento, California 95814 or by telephone at (916) 930-2664.
- d. The EPA and/or their applicant shall educate and inform personnel involved in the project as to the *Conservation Measures* and Terms and Conditions in this biological opinion.
- e. The EPA shall comply with the reporting requirements of this biological opinion, including a post-construction report outlining how the *Conservation Measures* were implemented for this project.
- f. The EPA and/or their applicant shall ensure any personnel identified as biological monitors or biologists, who are responsible for ensuring compliance with the *Conservation Measures* or other parts of the project which may affect federally-listed species, be Service-approved prior to implementing those activities.

Reporting Requirements

In order to monitor whether the amount or extent of incidental take anticipated from implementation of the project is approached or exceeded, the EPA shall adhere to the following reporting requirements. Should this anticipated amount or extent of incidental take be exceeded, the Corps must reinitiate formal consultation as per 50 CFR § 402.16.

1. The Service must be notified within 24 hours of the finding of any injured or dead listed species or any unanticipated damage to its habitat associated with the proposed project. Injured listed species shall be cared by a licensed veterinarian or other qualified person, such as the Service-approved biologist for the proposed project. Notification will be made to the contact above in Term and Condition 1c, and must include the date, time, and precise location of the individual/incident clearly indicated on a U.S. Geological Survey 7.5 minute quadrangle or other maps at a finer scale, as requested by the Service, and any other pertinent information. When an injured or dead individual of the listed species is

found, the Corps shall follow the steps outlined in the Salvage and Disposition of Individuals Taken section below.

2. Sightings of any listed or sensitive animal species shall be reported to the Service and the California Natural Diversity Database (<https://www.wildlife.ca.gov/Data/CNDDDB/Submitting-Data>).
3. The EPA's applicant shall submit a post-construction compliance report prepared by the on-site biologist to the San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office within 60 calendar days of the date of the completion of construction activities. This report shall detail (i) dates that construction occurred; (ii) pertinent information concerning the success of the project in meeting the avoidance and minimization measures; (iii) an explanation of failure to meet such measures, if any; (iv) known project effects on the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail, if any; (v) occurrences of incidental take of this listed species, if any; (vi) documentation of employee environmental education; and (vii) other pertinent information.

Salvage and Disposition of Individuals

Injured listed species must be cared for by a licensed veterinarian or other qualified person(s), such as the Service-approved biologist. Dead individuals must be sealed in a resealable plastic bag containing a paper with the date and time when the animal was found, the location where it was found, and the name of the person who found it, and the bag containing the specimen frozen in a freezer located in a secure site, until instructions are received from the Service regarding the disposition of the dead specimen. The Service contact persons are the Assistant Field Supervisor of the Endangered Species Division at (916) 930-2664; and the Resident Agent-in-Charge of the Service's Office of Law Enforcement, 5622 Price Way, McClellan, California 95562, at (916) 569-8444.

CONSERVATION RECOMMENDATIONS

Section 7(a)(1) of the Act directs Federal agencies to utilize their authorities to further the purposes of the Act by carrying out conservation programs for the benefit of endangered and threatened species. Conservation recommendations are discretionary agency activities to minimize or avoid adverse effects of a proposed action on listed species or critical habitat, to help implement recovery plans, or to develop information. The Service recommends the following actions:

1. Encourage or require the use of appropriate California native species in restoration efforts.
2. Facilitate additional educational programs geared toward the importance and conservation of tidal marsh and seasonal wetlands.
3. Assist the Service with implementing other recovery actions identified within the most current recovery plans for salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail.

In order for the Service to be kept informed of actions minimizing or avoiding adverse effects or benefiting listed species or their habitats, the Service requests notification of the implementation of any conservation recommendations.

REINITIATION – CLOSING STATEMENT

This concludes formal consultation on the City of Sunnyvale's Cleanwater Program Phase 2 Project. As provided in 50 CFR § 402.16,

- 1) Reinitiation of formal consultation is required and shall be requested by the Federal agency or by the Service where discretionary Federal agency involvement or control over the action has been retained or is authorized by law and:
 - A) If the amount or extent of taking specified in the incidental take statement is exceeded;
 - B) If new information reveals effects of the action that may affect listed species or critical habitat in a manner or to an extent not previously considered;
 - C) If the identified action is subsequently modified in a manner that causes an effect to the listed species or critical habitat that was not considered in the biological opinion; or
 - D) If a new species is listed or critical habitat designated that may be affected by the identified action.

- 2) An agency shall not be required to reinitiate consultation after the approval of a land management plan prepared pursuant to 43 U.S.C. 1712 or 16 U.S.C. 1604 upon listing of a new species or designation of new critical habitat if the land management plan has been adopted by the agency as of the date of listing or designation, provided that any authorized actions that may affect the newly listed species or designated critical habitat will be addressed through a separate action-specific consultation. This exception to reinitiation of consultation shall not apply to those land management plans prepared pursuant to 16 U.S.C. 1604 if:
 - A) Fifteen years have passed since the date the agency adopted the land management plan prepared pursuant to 16 U.S.C. 1604; and
 - B) Five years have passed since the enactment of Public Law 115-141 [March 23, 2018] or the date of the listing of a species or the designation of critical habitat, whichever is later.

If you have any questions regarding this biological opinion, please contact Kim Squires, Section 7 Division Manager (Kim_Squires@fws.gov) at the letterhead address or at or at 916-930-5634. Please reference the Service File Number 08FBDT00-2020-F-0111 in any correspondence regarding this project.

Sincerely,

Jana Affonso
Acting Field Supervisor

LITERATURE CITED

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- U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service. 2020. 5-YEAR REVIEW: California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*). San Francisco Bay-Delta Office, Sacramento, California. 33 pp.
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